

Use of The "Six Hat" Method when working on text analysis

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Abstract:

The article covers a wide range of issues related to the development of oral and written speech in the process of working on the text of junior schoolchildren. The students were also told about the importance of developing problem-solving and critical thinking skills. The essence of the Six Hats methodology, developed by Edward de Bono, is revealed in developing students' parallel thinking skills. Using the Six Hats method, students are able to analyze the text in a comprehensive way. This develops students' ability to not only learn the content of a text, but also to express their attitude toward the text.

Keywords: literature, text, analysis, method, hat, fact, emotion, preference, criticism, conclusion, creativity, thinking, reasoning, attitude, accuracy,

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INTRODUCTION

Fiction is a special way of knowing. For a long time, teachers and methodologists believed that one reading of works of art at school was enough. But often the first reading cannot lead to full and convincing impressions and sensations. Then a brief analysis is needed so that readers can understand all the ideas and details of the painted by the author. It is only after learning this information that students will be able to experience an aesthetically correct and profound work of art.

MAIN PART

The Six Hats Method can be used effectively working with text analysis. The Six Hats method is also called the De Bono method. Because this method was developed by a British writer and psychologist, an expert in creative thinking **Edward de Bono**¹. The system of thinking of Edward de Bono was created in the second half of the XX century and contains revolutionary views on the structure of thinking, as well as on the possibility of increasing the efficiency of the ego, the development of human creativity. The system includes scientific, educational and practical aspects.

De Bono's most famous works include "Water Logic", "Literary Thinking", "Teach Yourself to Think", "Birth of a New Idea", "Serious Creative Thinking", "Six Hats of Thinking", "I'm Right - You're Misguided".

Edward de Bono's core book "The Mind Mechanism" was published in 1969, where he proposed a new approach to enterprise development based on the model of self-organizing information structure. One of the world's leading physicists, Nobel Prize winner **Murray Gell-Mann** said that this book is dedicated to the tenth anniversary of the work on the theory of chaos, nonlinear and self-organizing systems.

Based on this approach, Edward de Bono created the concept of lateral thinking and practical methods of applying ego. Traditional thinking is associated with analysis, judgment and discussion as the leading evaluation mechanism. In a stable world, this was not enough because, having identified typical situations, it could be developed for any standard solution. One thing is that in today's rapidly changing world, there is a huge need for new thinking - creative, constructive, enabling the creation of new ideas and ways of development. The methods proposed by Edouard de Bono are precisely the tools for such new thinking.

De Bono states that education is still oriented to load the student with the maximum amount of knowledge and facts, but does not teach him to think. More precisely, he teaches to think one-sidedly, focusing mainly on critical thinking. Critical thinking is necessary, but, not knowing the other tools, a person falls into a trap, he is not able to objectively consider all sides of the problem, to generate new ideas, to focus on the practical result of thinking.

De Bono noted the importance of the perception process in thinking. At school, people are used to abstracting from perception - they get tasks with ready input information. But in life it's not like that. Here the solution of a problem entirely depends on the initial perception of the problem. Especially valuable is observation in interpersonal relationships. In most

¹ Edward Charles Francis Publius de Bono was born May 19, 1933 in Malta. He is a graduate of St Martin's College, Malta; he received his doctorate in medicine from the University of Malta and later, as a Rhodes Scholar, he studied at Oxford, Christ Church College, where he received his master's degree in psychology. De Bono also received his PhD in medicine from Trinity College, Cambridge and his PhD in law from the University of Dundee..

cases, each of the participants in the discussion is right, but based on his or her own perception, which is based on his or her principles, values, education, knowledge, etc. With this in mind, one should not focus on persuading one's opponent, but on effective interaction that allows one to develop creative proposals that satisfy the true interests of the parties.

De Bono notes that up to now the widespread orientation is exclusively based on logical principles proposed by ancient Greek philosophers, is not able to effectively solve modern problems. In contrast, he offers his own - water logic (instead of traditional stone). For example, according to the accepted logic, the statement can be either true or false. And the water logic is more flexible - the glass may not be filled with water completely - "it is half full, and it is half empty". It is important that water logic has serious practical application. De Bono believes that the future is behind it. He rightly notes that the domination of stone logic has led to the blossoming of science and technology, but it has not advanced human relations at all - so far, conflicts are solved by force because of the inability to agree, to look at the problem more widely.

Let's consider one of the simplest and most effective methods of thinking, proposed by De Bono - Six Hats. The advantage of this method is that it can be used both for group and individual thinking, and you can learn it in just half an hour. It is not a secret that a person, reflecting on any problem, tries to "embrace the immensity" - at the same time looking for new ideas, analyzing their coherence, trying to abstract from emotions, making conclusions, etc. It turns out to be chaos, from which it is very difficult to extract something really valuable. De Bono identified six main types of thinking, each of which he marked with a hat of a certain color. He suggested that these types should be used sequentially in the process of thinking - by analogy with taking off and putting on hats.

The main idea of this method is parallel thinking. In other words, this method suggests looking at the problem (in our case over this text) with a different but clearly defined position. The problem can have some decisions, and six ways of thinking allow to see them all.

The main purpose of the method is to teach people to better understand the peculiarities of thinking, to control the way of thinking and to connect it more clearly with the tasks in order to use the thinking process more effectively in solving problems.

White hat: Figures and facts. Information. Questions. Incidents that are happening. Impartiality recording of group work. What information do we have? What kind of information do we need?

With a white hat, when you analyze a text, you only emphasize the facts and the main idea. You don't pay attention to other things.

Red hat: The power of emotion. Intuition. Does not require an excuse for feelings. How did the students (teachers) feel in the learning process?

The person wearing a red hat evaluates the text based on intuition, emotions and instincts. What emotions does the text evoke? Does it make you feel loved? Or is it interesting? Or a source of inspiration? Do you have anger? Or encouragement?

Black hat: Careful. Negative aspects of the process. What are the disadvantages? What mistakes were made?

The reader who wears it is looking for flaws in the text, and the more he/she finds them, the better. Incorrect, contradictory - resistance, problems, negative consequences - all this will be on the verge of the black hat.

Yellow hat: Benefits. What progress has been made in the process. Make positive conclusions. Why is that acceptable? What are the benefits? Why is this happening?

A yellow hat is the opposite of a black hat. That is, the reader who wears it only looks for the strong points of the text. Yellow hat has no drawbacks, there are only advantages, and its only job - to find the positive sides.

Green hat: creative approach. Different ideas. New insights. Suggestions. Different solution options. What are the alternatives? Ways to improve the process.

It's creative thinking. We ask ourselves the question: "What can be done differently, why and how?" This "hat" allows us to find new facets in the studied material.

Blue hat: Analysis. Overview. Decision making. What have we achieved? What do we do next?

The previous five hats only take up a certain part of the thinking process. In other words, they are responsible for only part of the work. The blue hat integrates these parts into one image. With a blue hat, you systematize ideas into white, red, black, green and yellow hats. The blue hat sums up all the work in the text. It answers the author's problematic questions.

The strategy of the Six Hats Method:

1. What information do we have?
2. How do you feel about that?
3. Is that right? What are the disadvantages?
4. What are the advantages?
5. New ideas. What's the alternative?
6. What have we done? What do we do next?

The Six Hats style is an attempt to learn to focus on different aspects of thinking at the same time. As a result, this combination of different aspects provides holistic thinking.

Advantages of the Six Hats method (to find them you need to use Yellow Hat):

- 1) Usually mental work seems boring and abstract. Six hats make it a colorful and fascinating way to control your thinking;
2. Colored hats are a well-remembered metaphor that is easy to teach and easy to apply;
3. the Six Hats Method can be used at any level of complexity, from kindergartens to boards of directors;
4. By structuring work and eliminating fruitless discussions, thinking becomes more focused, constructive and productive;
5. The hat metaphor is a kind of role-playing language in which it is easy to discuss and switch thinking, distracting from personal preferences and not hurting anyone;
6. The method avoids confusion because only one type of thinking is used by the whole group in a certain period of time;
7. The method recognizes the importance of all the components of work on the project - emotions, facts, criticism, new ideas - and includes them in the work at the right time, avoiding destructive factors.

Certainly, like any methodology, the system of thinking of Edward De Bono requires a period of patience for its assimilation: it is necessary to form a habit of thinking by the rules. But in return, the practitioner will receive:

- an increase in the efficiency of his or her thinking and, as a result, the decisions he or she makes;

- the pleasure of the thought process.

De Bono advises to develop creative thinking:

1. Get away from clichés and established patterns of thinking;

2. Doubt positively about the acceptable;

3. Generalize the alternatives;

4. Grab new ideas and see what happens;

5. Find new entry points that you can bounce off.

CONCLUSION

It should be noted that many of the difficulties and problems encountered in teaching creative thinking are related to the low qualifications of those who take up the subject. Since creative thinking at first glance does not require either logic or experience, all who are not lazy to learn it. The result is an "instant" expert in creative thinking. Many believe that this is the right approach. Others find themselves disappointed and biased. As a result, the idea of learning to think creatively devalues and is perceived at best as a tricky thing that can sometimes be useful.

Six metaphorical hats of different colours, each of which represents a basic type of thinking. They are designed for creative and constructive thinking that complements evaluation and analysis.

The use of Six Hats thinking allows teachers to easily move towards a model of personalized learning, seeing the student as a full partner in a collaborative pedagogical process. In addition, the use of techniques allows the creation of a playful, creative environment, thus forming important traits of the child's personality.

Using similar methods of working with text, our students will improve their ability to analyze the text and express their personal approaches to it, independent opinions.

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